

Environmental Harmony in Kishwar Desai's *The Sea of Innocence*

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The present paper investigates the environmental harmony in Kishwar Desai's *The Sea of Innocence*. The objective of the study is to focus on the environmental harmony in the *Sea of Innocence*.

The study uses qualitative research because this method the researcher is equivalent to analysing the environmental harmony in Kishwar Desai's *The Sea of Innocence*. This qualitative method is subjective and can give the research results in words or text. The data and sources are gathered from important books, journals, articles, and internet sources from the library

Kishwar Desai is an Indian novelist who emerged as one of the most influential writers. She has worked in some television. She writes about women's background in the modern society. She holds a very important place in Indian English detective fiction because her works give fresh insight into the existing form of Indian literature.

Kishwar Desai's Simran Singh Series novels are *Witness the Night* (2010) *Origins of Love* (2012), and *The Sea of Innocence* (2013). Kishwar Desai exposes a true picture of women's status in Indian society. She skilfully textures a serious social issue with many characters and subplots in the thread of mystery and suspense. Her novels are not just a source of entertainment but serve as a barometer of society.

The Sea of Innocence is a gripping detective story, but it is also the examination of a serious social problem. *The Sea of Innocence* illustrates the importance of Environmental Harmony and offers practical solutions for promoting sustainability and conservation. Arundhati Roy writes that *The Sea of Innocence* is a powerful exploration of the interconnectedness of human and environmental fate, but also a stark reminder of the consequences of our actions. Sunita Narain puts forth that "the novel exposes the harsh realities of environmental degradation and the need for collective action to protect our planet."

To conclude the novel *The Sea of Innocence* highlights the importance of living in harmony with nature, emphasizing the interconnectedness of human and natural systems. The novel advocates for a holistic approach to environmental harmony, considering the intricate relationships between human and natural systems.

Keywords: Environmental Harmony, Detective Fiction, Sustainability, Interconnectedness and Holistic Approach

Kishwar Desai has started her career as a print journalist and a political reporter. Kishwar Desai writes about women's background in the modern society. Kishwar Desai's Simran Singh Series novels are, *Witness the Night* (2010) *Origins of Love* (2012), and *The Sea of Innocence* (2013). Kishwar Desai portrays a true picture of women's position in Indian society. She expertly weaves a serious social issue with many characters and subplots in the thread of mystery and suspense. The novels of Kishwar Desai are not just a source of entertainment but serve as a barometer of society. Kishwar Desai's first novel *Witness the Night* (2010) honored her with the *Costa First Novel Award* 2010. She presents a vivid picture of the violence carried out in a male-dominated family to the feeble girl children.

B. Soundarya (2017) states;

"Simran Singh in *The Sea of Innocence* plays the societal roles traditionally assigned to an Indian woman. This novel has described about slack editorializing kills the tension in a relevant tale of rape and murder in India. Like all Desai's novels, *The Sea of Innocence* is a gripping detective story, but it is also the examination of a serious social problem". (P1)

Kishwar Desai's novels habitually explore themes of harmony in various contexts. the novel "*Witness the Night*" (2010) discovers the social harmony between a young girl and her family in a small town in India. The novel "*The Sea of Innocence*" (2013) highlights the social harmony between a British woman and her Indian driver in a small town in India. also explores the cultural harmony between British and Indian cultures in a small town in India. Ubbeti J. R, and Rama NH Alapati write that in the novel "*The Sea of Innocence*" Kishwar Desai highlights the significance of examining the experiences of both genders as victims of sexual violence and discrimination. Through this amalgamation, Desai tenaciously explores and reveals profound depths of human behavior that exist within specific sectors of the nation. p.4804)

The novel "*The Longest Night*" (2015) highlights the cultural harmony between Indian and Pakistani cultures during the Partition of India.

The concept of Environmental Harmony in English novels has evolved over time, reflecting changing attitudes towards nature and the environment. Here's a brief history:

- Romantic Era (1780-1830): Novels like Wordsworth's "*The Prelude*" and Coleridge's "*The Rime of the Ancient Mariner*" emphasized the beauty and power of nature, promoting a sense of harmony with the environment.
- Victorian Era (1830-1900): Novels like Dickens' "*Oliver Twist*" and Eliot's "*Middlemarch*" highlighted the impact of industrialization on the environment and human relationships, raising concerns about environmental harmony.
- Early 20th Century (1900-1945): Novels like Lawrence's "*The Rainbow*" and Woolf's "*Mrs. Dalloway*" explored the human relationship with nature, emphasizing the need for harmony and balance.
- Post-War Era (1945-1970): Novels like Golding's "*Lord of the Flies*" and Lessing's "*The Grass is Singing*" examined the impact of human actions on the environment, promoting environmental awareness and harmony.

- Environmental Movement (1970-1990): Novels like Abbey's "The Monkey Wrench Gang" and McEwan's "The Child in Time" reflected the growing environmental movement, emphasizing the need for harmony with nature.
- Contemporary Era (1990-present): Novels like McEwan's "Solar" and Atwood's "The Year of the Flood" address pressing environmental issues, promoting sustainability and harmony with the natural world.

Throughout this history, English novels have increasingly emphasized the importance of Environmental Harmony, reflecting changing societal attitudes and concerns.

In English Literature, "harmony" refers to *a state of balance, coherence, and concordance among different elements*, such as:

- a) Character relationships: Harmonious interactions and understanding between characters.
- b) Plot and structure: A balanced and coherent narrative structure.
- c) Themes and ideas: A unified and consistent exploration of themes and ideas.
- d) Nature and environment: A balance between human existence and the natural world.
- e) Inner self: A state of inner peace, balance, and coherence within a character.
- f) Social and cultural: Harmony among different social and cultural groups.
- g) Emotional and psychological: Balance and coherence in emotions, thoughts, and psychological well-being.

Here are various harmonies intertwined throughout the Sea of Innocence, creating a rich and nuanced exploration of human relationships and experiences are as bellow;

- a) **Environmental Harmony:** The novel the Sea of Innocence highlights the importance of living in harmony with nature, emphasizing the interconnectedness of human and natural systems.
- b) **Social Harmony:** The story explores the social harmony between characters from different backgrounds, cultures, and classes, promoting understanding and empathy.
- c) **Cultural Harmony:** The novel celebrates the cultural harmony between Indian and British cultures, showcasing the beauty of diversity and exchange.
- d) **Emotional Harmony:** The narrative delves into the emotional harmony of the protagonist, Simran, as she navigates her past, present, and relationships.
- e) **Inner Harmony:** The story explores Simran's journey towards inner harmony, as she confronts her demons and finds peace.
- f) **Spiritual Harmony:** The novel the Sea of Innocence touches on spiritual harmony, highlighting the importance of faith, hope, and resilience in the face of adversity.
- g) **Marital Harmony:** The narrative portrays the harmony in Simran's marriage, emphasizing the importance of communication, trust, and understanding.
- h) **Family Harmony:** The story explores the harmony within Simran's family, showcasing the beauty of relationships and the importance of forgiveness.
- i) **Community Harmony:** The novel, *the Sea of Innocence* highlights the harmony within the community, emphasizing the importance of social cohesion and collective responsibility.
- j) **Personal Harmony:** The narrative emphasizes the importance of personal harmony, encouraging readers to find balance and coherence in their own lives.

Environmental Harmony in "The Sea of Innocence"

- a. **Sustainable Fishing Practices:** The novel highlights the importance of sustainable fishing practices, such as catch-and-release fishing, to maintain the balance of marine ecosystems.
- b. **Marine Conservation:** The story emphasizes the need for marine conservation efforts, like establishing marine protected areas, to preserve biodiversity and protect endangered species.

- c. **Waste Management:** The novel showcases the impact of improper waste management on marine ecosystems and highlights the importance of reducing, reusing, and recycling waste.
- d. **Renewable Energy:** The story promotes the use of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, to reduce dependence on fossil fuels and mitigate climate change.
- e. **Ecotourism:** The novel demonstrates the benefits of responsible ecotourism, which supports local communities and promotes the conservation of marine ecosystems.
- f. **Climate Change Mitigation:** The story highlights the need for collective action to address climate change, including reducing carbon emissions and transitioning to sustainable practices.
- g. **Sustainable Livelihoods:** The novel emphasizes the importance of sustainable livelihoods, such as sustainable fishing and aquaculture, to support local communities and promote environmental stewardship.
- h. **Education and Awareness:** The novel displays the importance of education and consciousness in encouraging environmental harmony, and inspirational individuals to take action to defend the marine environment.

These examples from "The Sea of Innocence" illustrate the importance of Environmental Harmony and offer practical solutions for promoting sustainability and conservation. "The novel exposes the harsh realities of environmental degradation, but also offers a message of hope and resilience." (The Guardian) "Environmental degradation, in the sea of innocence" suggests a stark contrast between the purity and vulnerability of nature (represented by the "sea of innocence") and the harmful impact of human actions (environmental degradation). All this is discussed as below;

- i The destruction of pristine natural habitats and ecosystems, where wildlife and plants thrive in innocence, unaware of the harm caused by human activities.
- ii The pollution of our oceans, where marine life inhabits a seemingly endless and innocent blue expanse, yet faces the devastating consequences of human neglect and abuse.
- iii The loss of childhood innocence due to the growing awareness of environmental issues and the responsibilities that come with it.

Following lines in *The Sea of Innocence* highlights environmental degradation and its consequences, emphasizing the need for harmony with nature;

*"The sea of innocence was becoming a sea of despair, and we were all complicit in its destruction."
(TSI175)*

According to Kishwar Desai "The sea is a symbol of innocence, but also of the devastating impact of human actions on the environment." Kishwar Desai's novels often explore the complexities of human relationships and the importance of harmony in various contexts. Her works inspire readers to reflect on their relationships and experiences, promoting empathy and understanding. The following lines highlight **the symbolism of innocence** in the novel, emphasizing its beauty, fragility, and importance;

*"The sea of innocence was a reminder of the beauty and wonder that still existed in the world"
(TSI192)*

The following lines highlight the importance of **sustainable fishing practices** in the Sea of Innocence, emphasizing the need to respect the sea's resources and preserve its innocence for future generations.

"Sustainable fishing practices were like a drop of water in the ocean, a small but vital step towards preserving the sea's innocence." (TSI120)

Kishwar Desai's third novel *The Sea of Innocence* reflects the crude realities of an unsterilized political system and the contaminated social setups. The specialty of this novel is that; it traces the Delhi gang rape of Nirubaya which happened in 2012 (Limcy C., and Raj, R. Mayil.p.195). Desai highlights the crude realities

of social harmony in the novel, exposing the power struggles, inequalities, and oppressions that lie beneath the surface of seemingly harmonious communities. As she writes;

"In the sea of innocence, social harmony was a distant horizon, always receding, yet never disappearing from view." (TSI155)

We find the theme of Emotional Harmony in the novel, exploring the ups and downs of Simran's emotional journey and her quest for balance and inner peace. Here are some lines related to Emotional Harmony in "The Sea of Innocence" Kishwar Desai writes;

"The sea's vastness was like the expanse of her own emotions, a reminder that she was capable of depths and complexities beyond her wildest dreams." (TSI100)

In the novel, inner harmony is depicted as a dynamic and ongoing process, requiring effort, patience, and self-compassion. Simran's journey serves as a powerful reminder that inner harmony is essential for navigating life's complexities and finding peace amidst turmoil. Inner harmony in "The Sea of Innocence" refers to the state of balance, coherence, and peace within oneself. Here's a breakdown:

- a) **Balance:** Simran's journey is about finding the balance between her thoughts, emotions, and actions.
- b) **Coherence:** She seeks to align her inner self with her outer life, reconciling contradictions and inconsistencies.
- c) **Peace:** Inner harmony brings Simran a sense of calm, serenity, and contentment, even amidst life's challenges.
- d) **Self-awareness:** Simran's inner harmony requires her to understand herself, her values, and her place in the world.
- e) **Acceptance:** She learns to accept herself, others, and life's circumstances, embracing imperfections and uncertainties.
- f) **Mindfulness:** Simran cultivates mindfulness, being present in the moment, and letting go of attachments to thoughts and emotions.
- g) **Connection:** Inner harmony helps Simran connect with her inner self, others, and the natural world, fostering empathy and compassion.
- h) **Growth:** Through inner harmony, Simran experiences personal growth, developing resilience, and finding meaning and purpose.

"Inner harmony in the Sea of Innocence" is a captivating concept that evokes a sense of serenity and balance. It symbolizes the innate goodness and simplicity that exists within us all. This state of inner harmony allows individuals to navigate life's challenges with grace, wisdom, and peace, even amidst turmoil.

According to Mariyam Parveen the novel *The Sea of Innocence* is about the cataclysmic, gloomy, and nefarious world of rape in India. This novel is based on the real-life incident of gang rape and murder of British teenager Scarlett Keeling in Goa. In this novel Desai also recompenses tribute to the sixteenth December Delhi gang-rape victim as it was published immediately after the 'Nirbhaya case' (p.140). The "Gloomy World" serves as a counterpoint to the "Sea of Innocence", highlighting the complexities and challenges of life. Through Simran's journey, the novel shows that even in darkness, there is hope for growth, transformation, and ultimately, redemption.

The Complexities and Challenges in the Sea of Innocence

1. **Darkness within:** Simran faces her own inner demons, fears, and insecurities, which create a gloomy atmosphere.
2. **Social injustices:** She witnesses social and economic inequalities, exploitation, and oppression, which cast a shadow on her world.

3. **Environmental degradation:** The destruction of the natural world, pollution, and climate change contribute to the gloominess.
4. **Human suffering:** Simran sees the pain and struggles of those around her, including her family, friends, and community.
5. **Moral ambiguities:** She grapples with complex moral issues, gray areas, and difficult choices, adding to the gloom.
6. **Loss and grief:** Simran experiences personal losses and grieves for what's been lost, creating a somber mood.
7. **Fear and uncertainty:** The unknown and unpredictable nature of life creates fear and uncertainty, casting a gloomy shadow.
8. **Disillusionment:** Simran's idealism and innocence are challenged by harsh realities, leading to disillusionment and a sense of gloom. The following lines capture the essence of the "Gloomy World" in the novel, highlighting Simran's inner struggles and the darker aspects of life.

"The fishermen's nets were like the traps of her own mind, ensnaring her in a web of fears and doubts."
(p.38)

Amitav Ghosh writes "The novel, *The Sea of Innocence* highlights the intricate relationships between human and natural systems, but also reveals the darker aspects of human nature. "Thus the "Gloomy World" in "The Sea of Innocence" refers to the darker aspects of life that Simran encounters on her journey.

The results of this study indicate that the novel *The Sea of Innocence* highlights the interconnectedness of human and natural systems, emphasizing the need for harmony between the two. The novel underscores the importance of conservation efforts, such as protecting marine life and preserving natural habitats. The novel emphasizes individual responsibility toward environmental harmony, encouraging readers to make conscious choices in their daily lives.

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